

Design guidelines of a battery-to-HVDC power converter for hybrid electric regional aircraft

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Abstract

Aviation needs to transition towards the hybrid-electric aircraft to meet European Green Deal targets. This can only be accomplished with power distribution networks that can safely handle the high power and voltage levels, of up to several MW. This paper aims to present the first design steps and guidelines of a battery-to-HVDC power converter, currently under development within the European Project HECATE, granted under the HORIZON-JU-CLEAN-AVIATION-2022-01-HER-03 call and kicked-off in January 2023. The manuscript includes the design guidelines adopted in the area of power electronics and control, providing an overview of the advancements on the development of this battery-to-HVDC power converter, which poses a significant increase in power density target without sacrificing efficiency. In this paper, the comparison between two topology candidates, dimensioning, sizing, component pre-selection and design guidelines have been addressed as a previous step of its implementation in a fully functional prototype, keeping in mind compliance with aero regulations.

Introduction

Commercial aerospace evolution towards the More-Electric Aircraft (MEA) has involved operational and environmental benefits. Recent aircraft platforms (B787, A350, Embraer-E2...) utilize more-electric technologies to replace some of the legacy pneumatic and hydraulic systems, successfully demonstrating the potential for reducing weight and operating costs. However, the achievement of the stringent ACARE (Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe) emission reduction targets requires the aviation industry to shift drastically towards electric/hybrid-electric propulsion, also for larger aircrafts. This results in high power distribution levels. However, increasing the electrical power for powertrains, from hundreds of kW in contemporary electrical aircraft systems toward MW level full/hybrid electrical aircraft, is far from trivial.

In this context, the EU-funded HECATE (Hybrid Electric regional Aircraft distribution TEchnologies) project was granted under the call HORIZON-JU-CLEAN-AVIATION-2022-01-HER-03. The project addresses the challenges of system weight and power density, high voltage issues with lightning arcs and electromagnetic interference, as well as optimised thermal management. Additionally, it makes use of digital twins for the digitalisation of the design process.

The project aims to deliver a set of enabling technologies and provide a scalability roadmap towards CAJU Phase 2 flight demonstration and exploitation in a 2035-built hybrid-electric regional aircraft.

Within the enabling technology bricks under study in HECATE, power conversion components play a key role. They are a critical part of the electrical distribution architecture to ensure power is delivered at the required voltage levels within electrical distribution and to the loads. This paper focuses on the design of a high-power density dc-dc converter for connection to battery storage. The HVDC power converter aims at achieving the following advances beyond the current state of the art 2022 [1]:

- 40% increase of the power density, i.e. more than 10 kW/kg.
- Peak efficiency greater than 98.0 %.

1. Battery-to-HVDC power converter requirements

Top level requirements including input and output demands, operating conditions, reliability and safety, efficiency and power density, thermal management, interface, and testing and validation were defined in the first stage of the project. This enables the development of power converter technology that will be compatible with the electrical power system and will meet the

demanding needs of the hybrid electric aircraft.

The main requirements specified for the battery-to-HVDC power converter are listed in Table 1. Additionally, the following requirements are specified:

- The HVDC battery converter shall provide uni-directional power flow from the battery to the HVDC bus.
- The HVDC battery converter shall implement, at a minimum, protections for over voltage, over temperature, over current, and output short circuit.
- The HVDC Battery converter shall be designed to achieve a Design Assurance Level (DAL) B in accordance with DO-254.

2. Battery-to-HVDC power converter design guidelines

The converter is comprised of two main subsystems implemented through their respective PCB boards: the Control board and the Power Board. They are explained next.

2.1. General considerations

The reliability due to the requirements of the DAL B criteria is one of the key objectives. The criteria will be assessed according to the mission profile of an equipment in the avionics bay of a civil turboprop aircraft, which could be found in the FIDES standard. This standard is selected because it is up to date in comparison with other reliability methods.

2.2. Control board

The control stage will be developed around a microcontroller, family S32K3 from NXP, with support for Model Based Design (MBD), and different alternatives in the same package. It includes an integrated DSP to allow the HVDC power converter gate driving control, isolated from the HVDC bus. A high-level diagram of the proposed control board is

Requirement	Value
Continuous power capability	15 kW
HV Battery voltage range (V_{IN})	[270 - 443] V
Nominal HVDC voltage ($V_{OUT\ nom}$)	540 (+/-270) V
Aircraft Supply for the HVDC converter low voltage circuits	28 V

Table 1: Main requirements for the HVDC battery converter

illustrated in Figure 1.

The selection criteria are focused on DAL-B safety requirements. Software will be implemented with a lockstep processor, improving reliability of the system with an additional functional safety Power Management IC (PMIC). To achieve a good level of reliability, the design must be kept simple.

Regarding communications, ARINC 825 protocol will be considered. Additionally, the microcontroller includes capabilities to implement TSN (Time-Sensitive Networking) communications. Finally, the control board will be supplied by an isolated 28V from the LVDC bus, according to DO-160G.

2.3. Power Board

The power stage of the converter will be based on a three-level boost converter [2]-[3], including some recent technological advances, so as to achieve an improvement in power density with respect to the state of the art without compromising efficiency for a reasonable cost. Among these advances, the following are highlighted:

- Wide bandgap semiconductor-based modules for high frequency operation.
- Liquid cooling.
- Compact size high frequency passive components.

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of the proposed control board

Furthermore, digital control will be adopted for a higher versatility of the system, which allows the optimization of the control at different operating points. Also, by leveraging the high switching frequency along with the three-level operation, the size of both EMI (Electro-Magnetic Interference) filter and boost inductor are reduced.

Although the requirements for this converter only demand a unidirectional power flow, a bidirectional implementation was chosen due to future needs that may arise and the reduction in losses due to the replacement of diodes with MOSFETs.

3. Analysis and Comparison of topologies

3.1. Introduction

To tackle the converter design and development, two different topologies have been assessed, namely: interleaved boost and three-level boost bidirectional converters, as depicted in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively, including sensors and excluding any sort of sources and loads. They are widely known and have been previously described and analysed in the literature, as in [2]-[4]. In Section 3.3, an updated thorough evaluation has been carried out, using modern tools and components, such as:

- Automated simulations using PLECS® software, by utilizing semiconductor manufacturers' curves for both conduction and switching losses.
- Silicon Carbide power modules.
- Improved magnetic materials, in particular, amorphous and nanocrystalline ones, due to their simultaneous advantageous properties in terms of high frequency and saturation levels.

Fig. 2: Two-phase interleaved boost converter

3.2. Analysis

Before proceeding with simulations in Section 3.3, analytical evaluation of the topologies has been done, starting from the formulation set out in previous works. Since the equations related to conventional boost converter are broadly known, only those corresponding to three-level boost are explained next. These can be divided into two operating modes governed by different equations, namely for $V_{IN} < V_{OUT}/2$ and for $V_{IN} > V_{OUT}/2$. In both cases equations (1)-(2) apply, corresponding to the duty cycle and output capacitors as a function of voltage ripple specification, neglecting the contribution from the equivalent series resistance:

$$d = 1 - \frac{V_{IN}}{V_{OUT}} \quad (1)$$

$$C = \frac{I_{OUT} \cdot d}{f_{SW} \cdot \Delta V} \quad (2)$$

Regarding inductor values depending on the current ripples specified, (3) applies for $V_{IN} < V_{OUT}/2$ and (4) for $V_{IN} > V_{OUT}/2$.

$$L_1 = \frac{V_{IN} \cdot (d - 0.5)}{f_{SW} \cdot \Delta I} \quad (3)$$

$$L_2 = \frac{(2 \cdot V_{IN} - V_{OUT}) \cdot d}{2 \cdot f_{SW} \cdot \Delta I} \quad (4)$$

From all of the above, the following can be drawn:

- Output capacitors and input inductor are chosen for the worst V_{IN} and V_{OUT} combinations in terms of voltage and current ripples, respectively.

Fig. 3: Three-level boost converter

- Current ripple at the inductor is lower for the three-level boost, which translates into lower rms values and core losses for the inductor. Besides, the number of inductors, current sensors and current loop controllers is divided by two.
- Mosfet voltage rating is the half for the three-level, which theoretically could lead to reduce conduction losses due to the narrowing of the channel for lower voltage devices, albeit since most of the power modules are rated and optimized for 1200V, this feature shall not be exploited as it should.

3.3. Results

After developing the analytical study in the previous section, in this one a complete range of simulations has been carried out both to validate analytical results and to account for the losses in the semiconductors by using the data from the manufacturers, which leads to a higher degree of accuracy. Ripple values have been accurately predicted, whereas power losses are shown in Figure 4 for the switching frequency, power module and ambient temperature from Table 2, while passive components were chosen to have same current and voltage ripples at the input and output, respectively.

It is remarkable that both analysed topologies have very similar results, however, with respect to the magnetic component, which has a prominent influence on the final cost and volume, it is advantageous in the case of the three-level boost, which finally constitutes the main reason for its selection. Other desirable features from the interleaved boost such as the scalable number of phases and the possibility of switching off some phases according to the power level to increase efficiency, are considered of minor importance here due to the power level involved and the almost constant power regime.

Therefore, after the aforementioned advantages, it has been concluded the adoption of the three-level boost topology to implement the battery-to-HVDC power converter.

4. Final design

The innovation of this development lies in the application of new materials and components to a well-

Fig. 4: Simulated power losses for the evaluated power topologies and worst V_{IN} , V_{OUT} voltage combinations in terms of losses

known topology with the objective of achieving the highest power density without sacrificing efficiency but keeping in mind the stringent requirements of an aerospace application, which has been addressed in Section 1.

It is noticeable, as highlighted in Table 2, the low value of the passive components, despite the low ripple achieved (as indicated in Table 2), thanks to the high switching frequency operation, the multilevel topology and the proper components selection. For the present work, a high-frequency inductor has been devised, by using nanocrystalline material [5] for the core, allowing high frequency operation and high saturation values simultaneously, achieving an incredible compact size (45x52x30 mm) despite the high frequency and current levels present at this application. Since its reduction in size is already considerable, other approaches such as coupled inductors and planar components [6] have been discarded.

With regards to the embedded software, S32K344 from NXP has been chosen, due to its prominent capabilities in terms of Real-time computing and Safety (two lockstep 160 MHz floating-point cores) and Communications.

Control law, which shall be downloaded and tested with the arrival of the prototypes, has been implemented in one of the cores using a cascaded PI controller representing an outer voltage loop and an inner average control loop, apart from the due soft-start and protections.

Boost Inductor	14 μ H
Output Capacitors	10 μ F
Switching Frequency	250 kHz
Boost Inductor current ripple	11.5 A _{P-P}
Output Capacitors voltage ripple	4 V _{RMS}
Power Module	MSCSM120HM 16CTBL3NG
Maximum ambient temperature	70 °C

Table 2: Preliminary power stage components and specifications

Conclusions

The design guidelines and requirements of a battery-to-HVDC power converter for the interface between the HV battery and the HVDC bus have been addressed here, assessing recent materials and components applied to two power topologies with the same number of semiconductors: the two-phase interleaved boost and the three-level boost converters.

Aeronautical regulations were followed to select components and to comply with design directives (protections, interfaces...), driving to the design of a high-power density and high-efficiency power converter. Furthermore, the corresponding control algorithms, both high level and low level, have been developed to run on a platform with safety concepts. One key aspect is achieving DAL-B reliability levels, keeping in mind the power density and flexibility required in the system. In order to ensure system reliability, evaluations under FIDES standard will be performed.

On a later stage of the project, the implementation and

test of the battery-to-HVDC power converter shall be carried out.

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